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External Scientific Report

PPP exposure models for 3D orchards considering spraying technologies in Southern Europe

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3D-orchards – Appendix D

Appendix D – Inspected equipment

D.1. Most widespread inspected equipment: Airblast sprayers

Circular-shaped air conveyor

Circular-shaped air conveyor INVERTED FAN

3D-orchards – Appendix D

Tower-shaped air conveyor + Deflectors

Circular-shaped air conveyor + Deflectors

Triangular-shaped air conveyor

3D-orchards – Appendix D

Tower-shaped air conveyor

3D-orchards – Appendix D

D.2. Most widespread inspected equipment: other sprayers

Pneumatic sprayer

Sprayers without fan

3D-orchards – Appendix D

Hoses-and-guns

Drift recovery

3D-orchards – Appendix D

Small boom sprayer for herbicide application in 3d crops

3D-orchards – Appendix D

D.3. Different sprayer according to land characteristics

Which are the land characteristics? Different land characteristics require different spray equipment to be used

Flat area

3D-orchards – Appendix D Hill area

3D-orchards – Appendix D Mountain area

3D-orchards – Appendix D

D.4. Different equipment for 1 crop: citrus

Citrus airblaster circular + deflector

Citrus pneumatic

3D-orchards – Appendix D

Citrus airblaster 'triangular'

Citrus airblaster tower

Citrus airblaster circular

3D-orchards – Appendix D

D.5. Different equipment for 1 crop: vines

Vine for wine airblaster special deflector + canyon

Vineyard pneumatic 2 faces

3D-orchards – Appendix D

Vine for fresh consumption under mesh airblaster circular

Vines - Tower shaped air conveyor

D.6. Spray drift reduction techniques mainly present

Drift reduction nozzles

3D-orchards – Appendix D

Air deflectors

Device to manually adjust airflow

3D-orchards – Appendix D

D.7. Major problems in sprayers during inspections

Broken filter

3D-orchards – Appendix D Problems with power transmission shields

Bad nozzle condition: impossible identification and/or off-range flow

Inexistence or ineffective anti-drip devices

3D-orchards – Appendix D

Measurement & control system

Inadequate or malfunctioning

Deficient fan protections (1)

3D-orchards – Appendix D

Deficient fan protections (2)

Damaged filter in the tank filling opening

Leakage from the filling tank opening

Impossibility of emptying the tank

Inadequate or ineffective tank level indicator

3D-orchards – Appendix D without leakage

Irregular flow, leakage from the pump